

Report on Maturity of LLVM's Fortran Support

OpenMP and Language support

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Executive Summary

This report summarises our findings on the maturity of Flang, the Fortran compiler of the LLVM project.

We have analysed two important aspects for the DARE project: the current OpenMP support, and then the general compliance and correctness of the implementation based on existing Fortran testsuites.

We can conclude that Flang delivers a reasonable level of compliance in the language but the OpenMP support is still a bit lacking, specially for features that go beyond OpenMP 2.5. However the support is slightly scattered and is influenced by how difficult it is to implement OpenMP functionalities in the existing LLVM infrastructure.

Introduction

The Fortran programming language is still very popular in the HPC space. A significant number of libraries and applications have been written in Fortran and it is important to preserve the investment. Nowadays, alternative programming languages exist which can deliver the same performance and productivity as Fortran, but the costs of migration and later (re-)validation of the algorithms and applications makes this prohibitive.

Compared to other general purpose programming languages, Fortran remains a niche language. Some renewed interest has been seen in the last years due to new projects such as LLVM's Flang and lfortran projects along with the fact that foundational linear algebra libraries that can be used to power ML/AI kernels are implemented using Fortran, makes the language niche but relevant.

As part of the DARE project we are interested in making the most of Fortran applications and libraries so they can be mapped in the best way possible to the hardware developed in DARE. The choice of the project has been the Flang, a recent development in the LLVM community. Due to Flang relative existence, when compared to other long-established Fortran compilers, a question arises: what is the level of maturity of Flang in order to tackle large applications and libraries.

This early report focuses on the correctness and compliance of the Fortran language as implemented by Flang. The DARE project will have to devote later efforts in assessing the performance of the code generated.

Methodology

The methodology we have used for this report to assess the maturity of Flang has focused on the correctness and feature support. It is a non-goal of this report to evaluate performance or quality of implementation.

We use as a baseline the capabilities of GNU Fortran when evaluating Flang. (An application should be possible to compile using GNU Fortran prior attempting to port it to Flang).

We have split the evaluation in two parts: OpenMP support and Fortran Language support.

OpenMP Support

OpenMP support has been assessed with the OpenMP 6.0 Examples document available at the time of writing in the OpenMP website [OpenMP]. Each example has been compiled invoking `flang` with the `-fopenmp` flag. If compilation succeeds to generate a program, we have also executed and verified the result aligns with what the example documentation states. Because not all examples are full programs, for those where it was not difficult to do, we have completed them into full programs, prior to execution.

Some of the testsuite that we have used to assess language support also include tests for OpenMP, these have been included in their respective sections. We make a summary of OpenMP later.

Fortran Language support

Language support is a much broader topic to assess at this point and typically done using conformance test suites.

Unfortunately there is no widely accepted Fortran test suite for Fortran 2018, the specification that Flang aims at implementing (the latest version of the Fortran specification, known as Fortran 2023 exists but includes minor additions and will not be considered here). The closest one at the time of writing is the Fujitsu Compiler Testsuite [Fujitsu]. The LLVM Community is already using this testsuite for bug reporting. The LLVM testsuite [LLVM Testsuite] also includes a number of Fortran tests taken from GNU Fortran. Flang cannot pass all these tests: either due to missing functionality or GNU Fortran specific support. These tests are explicitly disabled.

For this reason, the methodology used for the language support will be based on gathering the currently disabled tests in the LLVM testsuite. We have excluded from this list tests that are GNU Fortran extensions not implemented by Flang.

For the Fujitsu Compiler Testsuite, due to its large number of tests, we have decided to run it fully.

Classification of the results

There are a number of failure scenarios that we have classified in section "Implementation Issues". Our goal is to pinpoint, to the best of our capacity, the component of Flang that is responsible for the failure, not in the sense of a defect but a lack of implemented functionality.

OpenMP support

This section summarises the results based on testing the OpenMP 6.0 Examples document. This document is at the time of writing this report incomplete in the examples (an update is in the works) so we may not have explicit evidence of missing

Parallel Execution

Table 1: Test results of the examples on the Parallel Execution chapter

Directive / construct	Example file name	Compile	Run	Notes
parallel do	ploop.1	Success	Success	
parallel	parallel.1	Success	Success	
teams	host_teams.1	Success	Success	warning simd information on composite construct discarded
parallel	nthrs_nesting.1	Success	Success	OMP: Info #276: omp_set_nested routine deprecated, please use omp_set_max_active_levels instead.
num_threads omp_set_dynamic	nthrs_dynamic.1	Success	Success	
	nthrs_dynamic.2	Error	-	Expected Semantic error
do	fort_do.1	Success	Success	
	fort_do.2	Error	-	Expected Semantic error
nowait	nowait.1	Success	Success	
	nowait.2	Success	Success	
collapse	collapse.1	Success	Success	
	collapse.2	Success	Success	
	collapse.3	Success	Success	
	collapse.4	Success	Success	
linear	linear_in_loop.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: Unhandled clause LINEAR in DO construct
sections	psections.1	Success	Success	
firstprivate in sections	fpriv_sections.1	Success	Success	
single	single.1	Success	Success	
workshare	workshare.1	Success	Success	
	workshare.2	Success	Success	

	workshare.3	Success	Success	
	workshare.4	Success	Success	
	workshare.5	Success	Success	
	workshare.6	Success	Success	non-conforming example
	workshare.7	Success	Success	
masked	masked.1	Success	Success	
loop	loop.1	Success	Success	
	loop.2	Success	Success	warning Detected standalone OpenMP `loop` directive with thread binding, the associated loop will be rewritten to `simd`.
omp_set_dynamic omp_set_num_threads	set_dynamic_nthrs.1	Success	Success	
omp_get_num_threads	get_nthrs.1	Success	Failure	Expected wrong behaviour
	get_nthrs.2	Success	Success	

OpenMP Affinity

Table 2: Test results of the examples on the OpenMP Affinity chapter

Directive / construct	Example file name	Compile	Run	Notes
proc_bind	affinity.1	Success	Success	
	affinity.2	Success	Success	
	affinity.3	Success	Success	
	affinity.4	Success	Success	
	affinity.5	Success	Success	
	affinity.6	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: Unhandled clause AFFINITY in TASK construct
omp_display _affinity omp_set_affi nity_format	affinity_display.1	Success	Success	
	affinity_display.2	Success	Success	OMP: Info #276 omp_set_nested routine deprecated, please use omp_set_max_active_levels instead.
	affinity_display.3	Success	Success	
	affinity_query.1	Success	Success	OMP: Info #276 omp_set_nested routine deprecated, please use omp_set_max_active_levels instead.

Tasking

Table 3: Test results of the examples on the Tasking chapter

Directive / construct	Example file name	Compile	Run	Notes
task	tasking.1	Success	Success	
task taskwait	tasking.2	Success	Success	
task single	tasking.3	Success	Success	
task shared taskwait	tasking.4	Success	Success	
task	tasking.5	Success	Success	
task untied	tasking.6	Success	Success	
task threadprivate	tasking.7	Success	Success	
	tasking.8	Success	Success	
task critical	tasking.9	Success	Success	
task locks	tasking.10	Success	Success	
task mergeable	tasking.11	Success	Success	
task mergeable	tasking.12	Success	Success	Expected unspecified result
final omp_in_final	tasking.13	Success	Success	
task if task final	tasking.14	Success	Success	
task priority	task_priority.1	Success	Success	
task depend	task_dep.1	Success	Success	
	task_dep.2	Success	Success	
	task_dep.3	Success	Success	
	task_dep.4	Success	Success	
task depend	task_dep.4b	Success	Success	
	task_dep.5	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: array sections not supported for task depend
	task_dep.6	Error	-	MLIR Lowering

	task_dep.7	Error	-	not yet implemented: Unhandled clause DEPEND in TASKWAIT construct
	task_dep.8	Error	-	
	task_dep.9	Success	Success	
	task_dep.10	Success	Success	
	task_dep.11	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: array sections not supported for task depend
	task_dep.12	Success	Success	
	task_dep.13	Success	Failure	wrong result <i>omp_all_memory</i> doesn't work
task depend transparent	task_dep.14	Error	-	Parser Doesn't accept <i>parallel</i> and <i>single</i> in the same line Parser <i>transparent</i> doesn't exist
task detach	task_detach.1	Success	Success	
taskgroup	taskgroup.1	Success	Success	
taskyield	taskyield.1	Success	Success	
taskloop	taskloop.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: Taskloop construct
	taskloop.2	Error	-	
parallel masked taskloop	parallel_masked_ta skloop.1	Error	-	
taskloop task_iteration	taskloop_dep.1	Error	-	Parser <i>task_iteration</i> doesn't exist
	taskloop_dep.2	Error	-	

Devices

To assess the correct support of the directives and constructs on this chapter we only checked for correct behaviour compiling the examples as we experienced difficulties using the debug device at the moment of writing this report.

Table 4: Test results of the examples on the Devices chapter

Directive / construct	Example file name	Compile	Run	Notes
target map	target.1	Success		
	target.2	Success		
	target.3	Success		
	target.4	Success		
	target.4b	Success		
target if	target.5	Success		
	target.6	Success		
reverse_offload target host	target_reverse_offload.7	Error		Semantic <i>declare target</i> must have an <i>enter</i> or a <i>link</i> clause
defaultmap	target_defaultmap.1	Error		Semantic can only have one <i>defaultmap</i> clause
declare mapper	target_ptr_map.5	-		Skipped <i>metadirective</i> doesn't work
allocatable target map	target_fort_allocatable_map.1	Success		
	target_fort_allocatable_map.2	Success		non-conforming example
	target_fort_allocatable_map.3	Success		non-conforming example
target map sections	array_sections.1	Success		it should give a compilation error
	array_sections.2	Success		
	array_sections.3	Success		
	array_sections.4	Success		
unified_shared_memory	usm_scalar_ptr_ref_asc.1	Success		
target update	array_shaping.1	Success		
declare mapper	target_mapper.1	Success		
declare mapper	target_mapper.2	Error		MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: <i>DEVICE</i> clause is not implemented yet
	target_mapper.3	Error		Semantic

				"previous declaration of default"
target data	target_data.1	Success		
	target_data.2	Success		
	target_data.3	Success		
	target_data.4	Success		
	target_data.5	Success		
target data if	target_data.6	Success		
	target_data.7	Success		
target enter exit	target_unstructure_d_data.1	Success		
target update	target_update.1	Success		
target update if	target_update.2	Success		
target update with mapper	target_update.3	Error		Semantic no symbol found for custom mapper
declare target	declare_target.1	Success		
	declare_target.2	Success		
declare target indirect	declare_target_indirect_call.1	Error		Parser <i>indirect</i> doesn't exist
declare target	declare_target.3	Success		
	declare_target.4	Success		
declare target declare simd	declare_target.5	-		Skipped <i>declare simd</i> doesn't work
declare target link	declare_target.6	Success		many link errors
declare target device_type	declare_target.7	Error		Parser <i>declare variant</i> doesn't exist
teams	teams.1	Success		
	teams.2	Error		MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: Unhandled clause reduction in omp.teams operation

target teams distribute	teams.3	Error	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: DEFAULTMAP clause is not implemented yet
	teams.4	Error	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: Unhandled clause reduction in omp.teams operation
target teams distribute simd	teams.5	Success	warning simd information on composite construct discarded
	teams.6	Success	
num_teams target	teams.7	Error	Parser <i>local</i> clause for <i>declare target</i> doesn't exist
target target device target data target teams	async_target.1	Error	LLVM
	async_target.2	Error	Semantic in a <i>target</i> construct a variable is not allowed to be in both <i>map</i> and <i>shared</i> clauses
	async_target.3	Success	
	async_target.4	Error	LLVM
	async_target.5	Error	Parser <i>nowait</i> clause in <i>target</i> doesn't exist
omp_is_initial_device	device.1	Error	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: DEVICE clause is not implemented yet
omp_get_num_devices	device.2	Success	
omp_set_default_device omp_get_default_device	device.3	Success	
	target_associate_ptr.1	Error	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: DEVICE clause is not implemented yet
omp_target_alloc omp_target_memcpy omp_target_free	device.4	Error	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: DEVICE clause is not implemented yet
	device.5	Error	
	device.6	Error	

SIMD

Table 5: Test results of the examples on the SIMD chapter

Directive / construct	Example file name	Compile	Run	Notes
simd	SIMD.1	Success	Success	
declare simd	SIMD.2	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: OpenMPDeclareSimdConstruct
simd reduction	SIMD.3	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: Unhandled clause reduction in omp.simd operation
simd safelen	SIMD.4	Success	Success	
simd collapse	SIMD.5	Success	Success	warning simd information on composite construct discarded
inbranch notinbranch	SIMD.6	-	-	Skipped <i>declare simd</i> is not implemented
	SIMD.7	-	-	
simd	SIMD.8	Success	Success	
declare simd linear simd linear declare simd uniform	linear_modifier.1	Error		Semantic The list item `p` specified with the REF 'linear-modifier' must be polymorphic variable, assumed-shape array, or a variable with the `ALLOCATABLE` attribute MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: Unhandled clause LINEAR in SIMD construct
	linear_modifier.2	Error		
	linear_modifier.3	Error		

Loop Transformations

Table 6: Test results of the examples on the Loop Transformations chapter

Directive / construct	Example file name	Compile	Run	Notes
tile	tile.1	Error	-	Semantic doesn't allow <i>tile</i> directive after a <i>parallel do</i> doesn't allow <i>tile</i> directive that isn't immediately followed by a <i>do</i> loop construct
	tile.2	Error	-	
	partial_tile.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: Unhandled loop directive (<i>tile</i>) Skipped <i>tile</i> directive doesn't work
	partial_tile.2	-	-	
unroll	unroll.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: Unhandled loop directive (<i>unroll</i>)
	unroll.2	Error	-	Semantic doesn't allow <i>unroll</i> directive after a <i>do</i>
	unroll.3	-	-	Skipped <i>unroll</i> directive doesn't work
	unroll.4	-	-	
apply	apply_syntax.1	-	-	Skipped <i>tile</i> directive doesn't work <i>unroll</i> directive doesn't work
	apply_syntax_equivalent.1	-	-	
	apply_syntax.2	-	-	
	apply_syntax_equivalent.2	Error	-	Parser <i>interchange</i> doesn't exist
	apply_syntax.3	-	-	Skipped <i>tile</i> directive doesn't work <i>unroll</i> directive doesn't work
apply_syntax_equivalent.3	-	-		

apply	apply_span.1	-	-	Skipped <i>tile</i> directive doesn't work
	apply_span_equivalent.1	Error	-	Parser <i>interchange</i> doesn't exist <i>reverse</i> doesn't exist
	apply_nested.1	-	-	Skipped <i>reverse</i> doesn't work <i>tile</i> directive doesn't work
	apply_nested_equivalent.1	-	-	Skipped <i>reverse</i> doesn't work <i>unroll</i> directive doesn't work

Synchronizations

Table 7: Test results of the examples on the Synchronizations chapter

Directive / construct	Example file name	Compile	Run	Notes
critical	critical.1	Success	Success	
	critical.2	Success	Success	
	worksharing_critical.1	Success	Success	
barrier	barrier_regions.1	Success	Success	
atomic	atomic.1	Success	Success	
	atomic.2	Success	Success	
	atomic.3	Success	Success	warning The syntax "FLUSH clause (object, ...)" has been deprecated, use "FLUSH(object, ...) clause" instead
atomic	atomic_restrict.1	Success	Failure	non-conforming example
	atomic_restrict.2	Success	Failure	non-conforming example
	atomic_restrict.3	Success	Failure	non-conforming example
atomic hint	atomic.4	Failure	-	warning hint clause discarded
acquire release	acquire_release.1	Success	Success	
	acquire_release.2	Success	Success	
	acquire_release.3	Success	Success	warning The syntax "FLUSH clause (object, ...)" has been deprecated, use "FLUSH(object, ...) clause" instead
	acquire_release.4	Success	Success	non-conforming example
ordered	ordered.1	Success	Success	
	ordered.2	Success	-	It should give a compilation error
	ordered.3	Success	Success	

depobj	depobj.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: OpenMPDepobjConstruct
doacross	doacross.1	Error	-	Parser <i>doacross</i> doesn't exist
	doacross.2	Error		
	doacross.3	Error		MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: OMPD_ordered
	doacross.4	Error		Parser <i>doacross</i> doesn't exist
omp_init_lock	init_lock.1	Success	Success	
omp_init_lock_with_hint	init_lock_with_hint.1	Success	Success	
omp_set_lock omp_unset_lock	lock_owner.1	Success	Success	
	simple_lock.1	Success	Success	
omp_set_nest_lock	nestable_lock.1	Success	Success	

Data Environment

Table 8: Test results of the examples on the Data Environment chapter

Directive / construct	Example file name	Compile	Run	Notes
threadprivate	threadprivate.1	Success	Success	
	threadprivate.2	Error		Expected Semantic error
	threadprivate.3	Error		Expected Semantic error
	threadprivate.4	Success	Success	
	threadprivate.5	Success	Success	
	threadprivate.6	Success	Success	
default(none)	default_none.1	Error		Expected Semantic error
private	private.1	Success	Success	
	private.2	Success	Success	non-conforming example
	private.3	Success	Success	
common shared private	fort_loopvar.1	Success	Success	
	fort_loopvar.2	Success	Success	
	fort_sp_common.1	Success	Success	
	fort_sp_common.2	Success	Success	
	fort_sp_common.3	Success	Success	
	fort_sp_common.4	Success	-	it should give a compilation error
fort_sp_common.5	Error	-	Expected Semantic error	
shared private	fort_sa_private.1	Success	Failure	Expected wrong result
	fort_sa_private.2	Success	Failure	Expected wrong result
	fort_sa_private.3	Success	Failure	Expected wrong result
	fort_sa_private.4	Success	Failure	Expected wrong result
	fort_sa_private.5	Success	Failure	Expected wrong result

	fort_shared_var.1	Success	Failure	Expected wrong result
lastprivate	lastprivate.1	Success	Success	
	lastprivate.2	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: lastprivate clause with CONDITIONAL modifier
reduction	reduction.1	Success	Success	
	reduction.2	Success	Success	
	reduction.3	Success	-	it should give a compilation error
	reduction.4	Success	Success	
	reduction.5	Success	Success	
	reduction.6	Success	Success	Expected race condition
	reduction.7	Success	Success	
task_reduction in_reduction	task_reduction.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: Unhandled clause TASK_REDUCTION in TASKGROUP construct
reduction(task)	task_reduction.2	Error	-	Semantic <i>reduction</i> with <i>task</i> clause is not allowed in a <i>parallel</i> directive
target reduction	target_reduction.1	-	-	Skipped <i>declare target</i> doesn't work
	target_reduction.2	-	-	
target task reduction	target_task_reducti on.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering Unhandled clause TASK_REDUCTION in TASKGROUP construct
	target_task_reducti on.2a	Error	-	Semantic <i>reduction</i> with <i>task</i> clause is not allowed in a <i>parallel</i> directive
	target_task_reducti on.2b	Error	-	
taskloop reduction	taskloop_reduction .1	-	-	Skipped <i>taskloop</i> is not implemented

	taskloop_reduction.2	-	-	
taskloop reduction simd	taskloop_simd_reduction.1	-	-	
scope reduction	scope_reduction.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: Scope construct
reduction private	priv_reduction.1	Success	Success	
	priv_reduction.2	Error	-	Parser doesn't accept <i>reduction</i> with <i>original(private)</i> clause
	priv_reduction.3	Error	-	Semantic problem with nested reductions
declare reduction	udr.1	Error	-	Parser <i>combiner</i> doesn't exist
	udr.2	Error	-	
	udr.3	Error	-	
	udr.4	Error	-	
induction	induction.1	Error	-	Parser <i>induction</i> doesn't exist
declare induction	induction.2	Error	-	Parser <i>declare induction</i> doesn't exist
scan	scan.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: Unhandled clause reduction with modifier in omp.wslloop operation
	scan.2	Error	-	
	scan.3	Error	-	Parser <i>scan init_complete</i> doesn't exist
copyin	copyin.1	Success	Success	
copyprivate	copyprivate.1	Success	Success	
	copyprivate.2	Success	Success	
	copyprivate.3	Success	Success	
	associate.1	Error	-	Expecter Semantic error

private with associate	associate.2	Success	Success	
	associate.3	Success	Success	
	associate.4	Success	-	Skipped can't test <i>target</i>

Memory Model

Table 10: Test results of the examples on the Memory Model chapter

Directive / construct	Example file name	Compile	Run	Notes
flush atomic	mem_model.1.f90	Success	Success	Expected result
	mem_model.2.f90	Success	Success	Expected result
	mem_model.3.f90	Success	Success	Expected result
	mem_model.4a.f90	Success	Success	Expected unspecified result
	mem_model.4b.f90	Success	Success	
allocators allocate	allocate.1.f90	Error	-	Semantic If list items within the ALLOCATORS directive have the SAVE attribute, are a common block name, or are declared in the scope of a module, then only predefined memory allocator parameters can be used in the allocator clause
	allocate.2.f90	Error	-	
	allocate.3.f90	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: OpenMPAllocatorsConstruct
	allocate.4.f90	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: OpenMPDeclarativeAllocate
	allocate.5.f90	Error	-	Parser <i>uses_allocators</i> doesn't exist
	allocate.6.f90	Error	-	Semantic <i>dynamic_allocators</i> after device construct not accepted
shared	fort_race.1.f90	Success	Success	Might cause a race condition

Program Control

Table 11: Test results of the examples on the Program Control chapter

Directive / construct	Example file name	Compile	Run	Notes
assume	assumption.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: OpenMP ASSUMES declaration
	assumption.2	Error	-	
	cond_comp.1	Success	Success	
	icv.1	Success	Success	OMP: Info #276 omp_set_nested routine deprecated, please use omp_set_max_active_levels instead.
	icv.2	Error	-	Parser <i>num_threads</i> with list doesn't work
	standalone.1	Error	-	Expected compilation error
	standalone.2	Success	Success	
cancellation cancel	cancellation.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: OpenMPCancelConstruct
	cancellation.2	Error	-	Parser error with if-then-else structure and directives
requires	requires.1	Success	-	Skipped can't test target
declare variant	declare_variant.1	Error	-	Parser <i>declare variant</i> doesn't exist
	declare_variant.2	Error	-	
metadirective begin metadirective	metadirective.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: DEVICE clause is not implemented yet
	metadirective.2	Error	-	Parser <i>begin metadirective</i> doesn't exist
	metadirective.3	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: METADIRECTIVE
	metadirective.4	Error	.	Parser <i>begin metadirective</i> doesn't exist

	selector_scoring.1	-	-	Skipped <i>declare variant</i> doesn't work
	selector_scoring.2	-	-	
dispatch	dispatch.1	-	-	Skipped <i>declare variant</i> doesn't work
parallel do	nested_loop.1	Success	Success	
	nested_loop.2	Success	Success	
parallel do barrier critical single	nesting_restrict.1	Error	-	Expected Semantic error
	nesting_restrict.2	Success	Success	non-conforming example
	nesting_restrict.3	Error	-	Expected Semantic error
	nesting_restrict.4	Error	-	Expected Semantic error
	nesting_restrict.5	Error	-	Expected Semantic error
	nesting_restrict.6	Error	-	Expected Semantic error
	target_offload_control.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: DEVICE clause is not implemented yet
	pause_resource.2a	Success	Success	
	pause_resource.2b	Success	Success	
do ordered do order(concurrent)	reproducible.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: Unhandled clause order in omp.wslloop operation
	reproducible.2			
omp_get_wtime	get_wtime.1	Success	Success	
omp_display_env	display_env.1	Success	Success	
error	error.1	Error	-	MLIR Lowering not yet implemented: OpenMPUtilityConstruct

Language Support

gfortran testsuite

Table 12 categorises the different compilation errors found when running the copy of the gfortran testsuite tests found in the llvm-test-suite.

Table 12: Non-supported Fortran 2018 features in Flang from the gfortran test suite

Feature / file	Error	Notes
legacy	flang either argument is unknown or is ignored	DEC compatibility: -fdec -fdec-char-conversions -fdec-blank-format-item -fdec-static -fdec-structure -ff2c DEC-style parameters
	Semantic No explicit type declared for <i>[sym]</i> <i>[sym]</i> is already declared in this scoping unit	cray pointers
	Semantic Unlimited format item list must contain a data edit descriptor Expected [FMT] edit descriptor .[SOMETHING] value	legacy format expressions
	Semantic Expected ',' or ')' in format expression	
	Semantic No intrinsic or user-defined ASSIGNMENT matches operand types [TYPE] and <i>hollerith constant</i>	Hollerith constant
	Semantic MLIR Lowering Expression cannot be converted to [TYPE] from <i>hollerith constant</i> Must have INTEGER type but its REAL (4) not yet implemented: BOZ	real indices BOZ literal constants

	Semantic	'[SYM]' may not be a procedure as it is in a COMMON block	procedure pointer inside COMMON block forbidden in F08
	Link	undefined reference to [sym]	f2c calling convention not supported, implying second underscore
20010216-1.f	llvm	64-bit code requested on a subtarget that doesn't support it!	
coarrays	MLIR Lowering	coarray intrinsic <i>lcobound</i> not implemented not yet implemented: coarray: ...	
GNU specific features / extensions	Semantic	No explicit type declared for [sym]	<i>access</i> and <i>chmod</i> and <i>cotand</i> functions
	flang	argument is unknown	-fallow-invalid-boz -funswitch-loops -finit-real= -finit-integer= -finit-character= -finit-logical -frecord-marker= -fno-range-check -ffpe-trap= -fmax-stack-var-size= -fmax-subrecord-length= -freal-4-real-10 -Wpedantic
	Semantic	Actual argument type [TYPE1] is not compatible with dummy argument type [TYPE2]	!GCC\$ attributes NO_ARG_CHECK
parameterized derived types	llvm	not yet implemented: parameterized derived types	
	Semantic	No intrinsic or user-defined ASSIGNMENT(=) matches operand types [TYPE 1] and [TYPE 2]	pdt initialization
	Semantic	Shape of initialized object [sym] must be constant	default value for pdts
	Semantic	Must be a constant value	len parameter not returned as constant
	Semantic	Derived type parameters of	pdt type extension

		allocatable object must be the same as the corresponding ones of SOURCE or MOLD expression	
pdt_20.f03	Semantic	'mask=' argument has unacceptable rank 0	
pdt_2.f03	Semantic	Actual argument type [TYPE1] is not compatible with dummy argument type [TYPE2]	these tests fail with a compilation error where gfortran would just give a warning or fail at runtime
iomsg_1.f90 iostat_2.f90 pr20163-2.f	Semantic	invalid STATUS value	
fmt_error_11.f03	Semantic	Unlimited format item list must contain a data edit descriptor	
module_procedure_4.f90 bounds_check_fail_1.f90 bounds_check_11.f90	Semantic	Subscript [m] is greater than upper bound [n] for dimension 1 of array	
namelist_use.f90	Semantic	[SYM] is already declared in this scoping unit	
procedure pointers	Semantic	'foo_size' is not a procedure	pr103312.f90
	Semantic	Procedure pointer may not be ELEMENTAL	proc_ptr_comp_45.f90
	Semantic	[sym] may not be a procedure as it is in a COMMON block	proc_ptr_common_1.f90
	Semantic	In assignment to procedure pointer 'funct', the target is not a procedure or procedure pointer	same name for symbol and function proc_ptr_47.f90
	Semantic	Procedure pointer 'op' with implicit interface may not be associated with procedure designator 'new_t' with explicit interface that cannot be called via an implicit interface	pr112407a.f90
	Semantic	Procedure pointer associated with result of reference to function that is an	proc_ptr_result_1.f90

		incompatible procedure pointer	
fmt_zero_digits.f90	Semantic	Positive scale factor k (from kP) and width d in a 'E' edit descriptor must satisfy 'k < d+2'	'(2PE15.0)'
intrinsic	Semantic	[sym] is not a known intrinsic procedure	lgamma, dacosh, dasinh, datanh, cos, zexp, zlog, zinc, zsqrt
and, or, xor	Semantic	Actual argument for 'i=' has bad type [TYPE]	bitwise operations with logical arguments
finalize_51.f90	Semantic	Result of pure function may not have an impure FINAL subroutine	
impure_1.f08	Semantic	In an elemental procedure reference with at least one array argument, actual argument that corresponds to an INTENT(OUT) or INTENT(INOUT) dummy argument must be an array	
interface_12.f90 result_in_spec.f90	Semantic	No explicit type declared for '[sym]'	character(f(x) function
entry_2.f90	Semantic	Result of ENTRY is not compatible with result of containing function	
submodule_31.f08 class_assign_1.f08	Semantic	[SYM] was not declared a separate module procedure	
impl_do_var_data.f90	Semantic	Must be a scalar value, but is a rank-1 array	
equiv_7.f90	Semantic	Equivalence set cannot contain arguments with distinct types that are not both numeric or character sequence types	equivalence with different types with similar structure
automatic	Parser	automatic attribute doesn't exist	
union	Semantic	not yet implemented: support for UNION	
minmax_char_1.f90	MLIR Lowering	not yet implemented: CHARACTER MIN and MAX with dynamically optional arguments	

selected_logical_kind_3.f90	Semantic	LOGICAL(KIND=-1) is not a supported type	result of <i>selected_logical_kind(12 8)</i>
PR95214.f90	Semantic	Actual argument variable length '1' does not match the expected length '77'	
class_dummy_6.f90	Semantic	A dim= argument is required for 'size' when the array is assumed-size	
class_dummy_7.f90	Semantic	Assumed-size polymorphic array may not be associated with a monomorphic dummy argument	
ieee_7.f90	Semantic	missing mandatory 'p=' argument	ieee_selected_real_kind(p)
ieee_8.f90	Semantic	Must be a constant value	parameter assignment
ieee_signbit_1.f90 minmax_2.f90 minmax_1.f90 minmax_3.f90 minmax_4.f90	Semantic	No specific function of generic <i>ieee_*</i> matches the actual arguments	
strictly-structured-block-1.f90	OpenMP	-	infinite compilation - probably caused by OpenMP annotations
char4_decl-2.f90 bind_c_char_10.f90 typecodes-array-char.f90 PR100906.f90 bind-c-contiguous-5.f90 bind-c-contiguous-1.f90 bind-c-contiguous-4.f90	Semantic	A BIND(C) object must have an interoperable type	
allocatable_length_2.f90	Semantic	Invalid specification expression: reference to OPTIONAL dummy argument '[sym]	assumed rank with optional and allocatable
c_kind_params.f90 continuation_19.f	flang	Only -std=f2018 is allowed currently	-std=c99 should only be passed to the main file not also to this fortran module
pr87689_0.f	Link	undefined symbol: doesntwork_p8	this test depends on another file but it is not explicitly declared in the main file
pr41576_0.f	Link	undefined symbol: main	the main is another file, but the run directive is in this file

selected_real_kind_2.f90	Link	undefined symbol: should_not_fail	the intention is that this reference should be eliminated as dead-code at compile time
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Execution tests

Most of the execution tests that fail are because LLVM's Flang does not fully replicate all of gfortran's functionalities or GNU-specific behaviours. These discrepancies often show in the implementation-defined specifics of I/O handling and error messages. These failures do not imply that Flang is incorrect.

Additionally, we skipped OpenMP tests as they are already covered in the previous section, and we did not consider OpenACC for these tests.

Fujitsu testsuite

We have also run the Fujitsu testsuite with results summarised in Table 13.

Table 13. Results of the Fujitsu testsuite

Test result	Number of tests
Passed	583134 (99.33%)
Failed to run	123 (0.21%)
Failed to compile	273 (0.46)

Tests that failed to compile were mainly due to lacking support for floating point types of 128-bits. These materialise in undefined references at link time. We also identified some problems with OpenMP threadprivate and the EQUIVALENCE statement which were not found in the earlier sections.

Tests that failed to run were mainly related to lack of correct behaviour of the OpenMP workshare construct. Other tests failed due to precision discrepancies between the reference output and the actual execution, we believe those are caused by the default setting of x86_64 not to include FMA instructions (Fujitsu testsuite has been tested on Arm64 bit, where FMA is available in the base ISA). At least one test failed due to the deprecated ENTRY statement.

Implementation Issues

Parser

These issues happen when Flang is unaware of the syntax. This results, typically, in errors of the kind “unexpected token”. Addressing this issue requires extending the grammar of F18 and also implementing the semantic support. An example of this is the `tile_size` clause in the `tile` OpenMP construct.

Semantic

These issues happen when Flang, though it is aware of the syntax and has support for it, it does not have the corresponding semantic support implemented. Most of these errors are flagged in the form of “unsupported” messages emitted by the compiler. An example of this is the support of `coarrays`. The parser recognises the syntax but most of the time does not implement the semantics and fails during the compilation.

MLIR Lowering

These issues happen when Flang fails to lower the semantic representation of the Fortran source code into MLIR. MLIR is a component of the LLVM IR project used extensively by Flang. Due to the pervasiveness of MLIR during the lowering process of Flang, errors may have different causes, but most of the problems are caused by the lowering itself still not being implemented. A class of issues in this step are parts of the programming language (or OpenMP) that, while being implemented both in the Parser and the Semantic, they do not have a representation in MLIR yet. The OpenMP `taskloop` construct is an example of this. Loop transformations are another example.

LLVM IR

Once the MLIR pipeline has been complete, Flang lowers it to LLVM IR which is used for further optimizations and the final code generation for the target (e.g., x86 or RISC-V). Issues here are caused by this lowering still missing, and we have identified a large number due to the `OpenMPIRBuilder` component of LLVM still not supporting a number of OpenMP constructs.

Recommendations for Fortran developers

In this section we propose a number of recommendations for Fortran developers when porting their code to build with Flang.

[R1] Ensure your code can be compiled with GNU Fortran and you are aware of GNU extensions (or other legacy extensions) that might complicate the porting. GNU Fortran compiler flags `-Wpedantic` and `-std=f2018` may help here [GNU Fortran Pedantic]. If you have been compiling with Intel Fortran, the command option `-stand f18` can help as well [Intel Fortran stand].

[R2] OpenMP support is rather limited at the time of writing this report. Enabling OpenMP may prevent compilation or lead to compiler crashes.

If your application allows disabling OpenMP, make sure the first porting step is done without OpenMP enabled.

Once you have validated the application correctness, OpenMP should be enabled and then at this point the application should be validated again.

Fundamental OpenMP constructs such as `parallel` and `do` should work but more advanced constructs or constructs of newer versions of OpenMP are still unimplemented.

At the time of writing this report, the `atomic` construct when applied to complex numbers is unstable. This may stabilise in the future.

The DARE project is committed at implementing support for the OpenMP constructs most valuable for the partners applications.

[R3] If possible, we recommend using a build system that supports Flang, such as `cmake 3.28` or later. Autotools can work with Flang but will likely fail at the link step when using old versions of `libtool` that are unaware of Flang when generating shared objects (i.e. dynamic libraries).

[R4] While the goal of Flang is to provide a compiler driver reasonably compatible with `gfortran`, not all the flags are supported. In particular the support for diagnostics (flags of the form `-W<something>`) is still lacking.

[R5] Some of the more advanced Fortran 2003 / 2008 / 2018 support is still lacking. In particular some of the object-oriented features have been reported as failures in the language support test suites.

[R6] Flang module files (`.mod` files, created as a subproduct of compilation of `MODULE` program units), as it already happens with the other major Fortran compilers, are incompatible with

other Fortran compilers and likely to be incompatible with different versions of the same compiler.

[R7] Support for 128-bit float types (`REAL(KIND=16)`) is not guaranteed on Flang. We believe these are not commonly used and should not be a problem.

Flang does support `REAL(KIND=2)` and `REAL(KIND=3)` for Float16 and bfloat. These are not supported, for now, in the LLVM-based compiler for DARE when targeting RISC-V.

[R8] The support for C interoperability (`ISO_C_BINDING`) in Flang is in good shape and we recommend it over legacy approaches based on observing what the C compiler does on a given platform.

Acronyms and Abbreviations

Each term should be bulleted with a definition.

Below is an initial list that should be adapted to the given deliverable.

- CA – Consortium Agreement
- D – deliverable
- DARE – Digital Autonomy with RISC-V in Europe
- DoA – Description of Action (Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement)
- EB – Executive Board
- EC – European Commission
- GA – General Assembly / Grant Agreement
- HPC – High Performance Computing
- IPR – Intellectual Property Right
- KPI – Key Performance Indicator
- M – Month
- MS – Milestones
- OpenMP – Open Multi Processing
- PM – Person month / Project manager
- WP – Work Package
- WPL – Work Package Leader

References

[Fortran 2018 JTC1/SC22/WG5] <https://wg5-fortran.org/f2018.html>

[Flang documentation] <https://flang.llvm.org/docs/>

[OpenMP] <https://www.openmp.org>

[Fujitsu] <https://github.com/fujitsu/compiler-test-suite>

[LLVM Testsuite] <https://github.com/llvm/llvm-test-suite>

[GNU Fortran Pedantic] <https://gcc.gnu.org/onlinedocs/gcc-15.1.0/qfortran/Error-and-Warning-Options.html>

[Intel Fortran Stand] <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/docs/fortran-compiler/developer-guide-reference/2025-1/stand.html>

